

Pilot Interview Outline

Q1. Can you describe your firm's **BIM experience level** (low, moderate, high)? And why do you believe it is at this level?

Q2. Can you reflect on the **level of BIM knowledge/awareness** in your consultancy firm. What are the **means** used in your firm to enhance your employees' BIM knowledge/awareness?

Q3. Can you reflect on the **level of BIM application** in your consultancy firm. For what **kind of applications** BIM is used, especially within the design process?

Q4. Do you think that the use of BIM is **too costly**? Or this cost is worth the investment.

Q5. Do you think that the implementation of BIM by consultancy firms in Kuwait requires extreme changes in their **organizational structures**? And why?

Q6. Do you think that the implementation of BIM by consultancy firms in Kuwait requires extreme changes in the firm's **organizational culture**? And why?

Q7. Do you think that there is enough **governmental support** to implement BIM in construction projects in Kuwait?

Q8. Is BIM **demanded by clients** in Kuwait either in the public or the private sector? And why?

Q9. What do you think are the **main driving forces** for the implementation of BIM by consultancy firms in Kuwait?

Q10. What do you think are the **top benefits** of the use of BIM by consultancy firms in Kuwait?

Q11. What do you think are the **major challenges/barriers/risks** (managerial, contextual, technical, financial, legal, contractual ...) behind the use of BIM in Kuwaiti's consultancy firms?

Q12. Finally, is there any other issues you want to address related to our topic and we did not cover in our previous questions?